

EEG Sensing to Assess Mental Fatigue Across Personality Traits Under Cognitive Load

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Abstract—Mental fatigue—a key factor in cognitive performance and well-being—varies markedly among individuals, yet personalized neurocognitive assessment methods are still emerging. To bridge this gap, we conducted an EEG-based study examining the relationship between mental fatigue dynamics and personality traits—specifically extroversion (comparing extroverts and introverts) and neuroticism (contrasting high vs. low levels)—to enable personalized fatigue profiling. To the best of authors' knowledge, this is the first study to establish such connections within this framework. Twenty-one participants completed cognitively demanding tasks (mental arithmetic and simulated job interviews) while EEG data were recorded using a wearable system. Subjective fatigue, measured post-task using the Chalder Fatigue Scale (CFS), revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between personality groups. Objective biomarkers were derived via spectral power analysis of EEG data from key frontal, temporal, central, and posterior regions. Two-tailed t-tests indicated that extroverts exhibited lower frontal fatigue, while temporal regions showed delta and theta differences for neuroticism and beta differences for extroversion. Central regions displayed spectral differences in all bands except delta and beta for extroversion, with the left central region showing significant differences across all bands for neuroticism. At the posterior region, fatigue variations were observed in all bands at the left posterior except theta band in extroversion and beta for neuroticism. Spatial brain maps further confirmed significantly lower fatigue in extroverts and low-neuroticism individuals, aligning with the subjective reports.

Index Terms—Mental fatigue, EEG, Cognitive performance, personality traits, wearable system, power spectral analysis, biomarkers

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental fatigue describes a state characterized by diminished energy, reduced concentration, and decreased alertness, which ultimately impairs cognitive performance [1]. Mental fatigue has emerged as a critical factor impairing quality of life by diminishing engagement levels, reducing task performance, intensifying anxiety, and degrading memory function [2]. A range of elements contribute to the onset of mental fatigue, including imbalanced workloads, excessive multitasking, poor physical health, sleep disorders, emotional instabil-

ity, chronic stress, monotonous tasks, physical exertion, and unfavorable environmental conditions [3]. Notably, psychological attributes such as personality traits also play a pivotal role in moderating the effects of fatigue, particularly under highly stressful conditions [4]. This underscores the urgent need for innovative methods capable of automatically detecting mental fatigue across diverse personality types, enabling personalized recommendations to foster healthier environments and promote mental well-being.

Mental fatigue has been extensively studied using psychological and physiological methods. Psychological approaches rely on subjective assessments, such as the Multidimensional Fatigue Scale (MFS), Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), Fatigue Symptoms Inventory (FSI), and Chalder Fatigue Scale (CFS) [5]. Physiological techniques leverage wearable sensors and AI to analyze fatigue through signals like EEG, ECG, GSR, and EMG. For instance, [6] integrated ECG, electrodermal activity (EDA), blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and skin temperature (SKT) with machine learning for fatigue classification. While EEG, EMG, ECG, and EDA have been widely explored [7], real-time fatigue monitoring remains a challenge, highlighting the need for innovative approaches to track fatigue progression dynamically.

Mental fatigue is closely linked to brain rhythms and has been shown to significantly influence neural activity. Research indicates that mental fatigue leads to alterations in EEG spectral power across delta (δ : 0.5 – 4 Hz), theta (θ : 4 – 8 Hz), alpha (α : 8 – 13 Hz), and beta (β : 13 – 30 Hz) bands [8]. An increase in θ -power reflects reduced arousal levels, while individuals experiencing fatigue often exhibit heightened α - and β -power, indicating increased vigilance and compensatory efforts to maintain attention. However, prolonged fatigue disrupts these patterns, leading to diminished engagement, reduced attention, and impaired task performance. These disruptions manifest as a shift in EEG activity from high-frequency, low-amplitude patterns to low-frequency, high-amplitude patterns, highlighting the profound impact of mental fatigue on brain dynamics [9]. In

[10], the relative band power derived from EEG signals is identified as a robust biomarker for recognizing fatigue. Likewise, [11] highlights that fatigue is associated with a decline in brain activity and cognitive capacity. Since EEG provides a direct reflection of users' mental fatigue, the power spectral density (PSD) analysis emerges as an exceptional approach for real-time assessment of fluctuating fatigue levels [8].

Mental fatigue levels, shaped by diverse psychological dimensions, vary across individuals. Here, we explore personality traits that drive fatigue in stressful contexts. As patterns of behavior, thought, and emotion, personality plays a vital role in well-being and serves as a key predictor of fatigue, being closely tied to numerous health-related and behavioral factors [12]. Among various personality traits, extroversion (characterized by a tendency toward sociability and energy) and neuroticism (marked by a tendency toward emotional instability) are closely linked to fatigue [13]. Research indicates that individuals with higher neuroticism levels experience greater cognitive fatigue, while lower extroversion is associated with increased physical fatigue [14]. Although numerous studies have explored the relationship between fatigue and personality traits, none have specifically focused on monitoring mental fatigue levels using EEG during various stressful situations. Some prior research has examined biomarkers of active and healthy aging across different personality traits [15] and the relationship between anxiety and personality through EEG recordings during video watching [16]. However, fatigue has not been objectively investigated under stress-inducing tasks. This study aims to assess mental fatigue by analyzing brain activity variations during such tasks. Furthermore, it is the first to evaluate fatigue differences among personality dimensions and explore how personality may act as a moderator of fatigue.

CONTRIBUTIONS

Our primary contributions are as follows:

- Developed a novel dataset for assessing mental fatigue in stressful environments by designing a unique framework to record EEG signals from 21 subjects during stress-inducing tasks on a computer.
- Conducted a statistical evaluation of mental fatigue in relation to extroversion and neuroticism personality traits.
- Quantified mental fatigue using the Chalder Fatigue Scale (CFS) and assessed personality traits with the Big Five Personality Questionnaire.
- Analyzed mental fatigue through spectral bands across two stages:
 - Mental arithmetic task (early stage),
 - Mock job interview (middle stage),

The paper is structured as follows: Section II details the methodology, Section III analyzes mental fatigue results, Section IV discusses findings, and Section V concludes with future research directions.

II. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure II presents an innovative framework for assessing mental fatigue through objective and subjective measures, integrating preprocessing, spectral analysis, and statistical evaluation across three phases.

A. Data Acquisition

1) *Subjects*: The study initially involved 21 healthy doctoral students (11 females, 10 males; mean age 28 ± 4 years). All participants reported no medical conditions, personality disorders, or vision impairments (normal or corrected). Data from 19 subjects were included in the analysis, while two participants were excluded due to excessive noise and muscle artifacts in their recordings.

2) *Experimental Equipments*: For EEG acquisition, electrodes were placed on the scalp following the international 10-20 system using an Ag/AgCl active electrode cap [17]. Signals were continuously recorded at 1024 Hz and streamed in real time via BioSemi's Active-View software, which provides visual feedback and customizable recording options. Nylon caps of various sizes ensured accurate electrode placement based on participants' head circumferences, and electrolyte gel was applied to enhance signal quality. Participants were seated comfortably at a standardized distance from a desktop computer during task performance.

3) *Experimental Procedure*: Participants were contacted a day prior to the experiment and provided with a personality questionnaire and consent form. On the experiment day, they were briefed about the study, seated in a quiet room, and fitted with the EEG setup, which took approximately 20 minutes. The experiment consisted of two phases:

- **Mental Arithmetic Task (5 minutes)**: Participants counted backward from 1022 in steps of 13. Correct answers earned 5 points, while incorrect answers deducted 10 points. Errors restarted the task, with feedback and a stopwatch displayed on the interface.
- **Job Interview (5 minutes)**: Participants spoke in front of a camera while being evaluated by a panel.

Participants rated fatigue using the CFS scale after each phase. The 40-minute trial is summarized in Fig. 2.

B. Signal Preprocessing

To enhance EEG signal quality, rigorous preprocessing was applied to remove artifacts like eye blinks and muscle movements [18]. A 1–45 Hz band-pass filter was used, followed by Autoreject and Independent

Fig. 1. Framework for assessing mental fatigue across personality traits under cognitive workload

Fig. 2. Experimental procedure for assessing mental fatigue in stress

Component Analysis (ICA) via MNE-Python. Autoreject segmented data into 2-second epochs, discarding noisy segments, while ICA further eliminated residual artifacts, ensuring high-quality signals for analysis

C. PSD-Based Feature Extraction Using Welch's Algorithm

We computed Power Spectral Density (PSD) from cleaned EEG signals using Welch's FFT-based method, a reliable approach validated in recent studies [19]. Five frequency bands were extracted: delta (0.5–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–13 Hz), beta (13–30 Hz), and gamma (30–45 Hz).

$$PSD(f) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K |\mathcal{F}\{x_k(t)\}|^2, \quad (1)$$

where $PSD(f)$ represents the power spectral density at frequency f , K is the number of segments, $x_k(t)$ is the k -th segment of the EEG signal, and $\mathcal{F}\{x_k(t)\}$ denotes the Fourier Transform of $x_k(t)$. The spectral bands were defined as follows:

- **Delta:** Δ (0.5 – 4 Hz)

- **Theta:** Θ (4 – 8 Hz)
- **Alpha:** α (8 – 12 Hz)
- **Beta:** β (12 – 30 Hz)

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Mental fatigue findings are analyzed through two approaches: (1) a subjective assessment of extroversion and neuroticism, and (2) an objective EEG-based evaluation of neural fatigue patterns across these personality dimensions. Both methods are detailed below.

A. Personality-Based Subjective Assessment of Perceived Fatigue

This section details the statistical analysis of perceived mental fatigue by extroversion and neuroticism. Participants were divided based on mean scores (19 for extroversion and 23 for neuroticism): those scoring above the mean were classified as extroverts (E, $n = 10$) and high neuroticism (More Neu, $n = 12$), while those below were categorized as introverts (I, $n = 9$) and low neuroticism (Less Neu, $n = 7$).

A two-tailed t-test ($p < 0.05$) assessed CFS score differences between personality groups.. Table I summarizes the results for both personality traits, extroversion, and neuroticism. It demonstrates a significant difference in mental fatigue levels between extroverts and introverts, as indicated by a p-value of less than 0.05. This distinction is further supported by the graphical representation in Fig. II(a). Similarly, the table highlights a significant difference in mental fatigue between individuals with high neuroticism (More Neu) and low neuroticism (Less Neu), with $p < 0.05$. The graphical representation in Fig. II(b) corroborates these findings, illustrating the differences observed between the two personality traits. The findings clearly demonstrate that extroverts experience significantly lower levels of mental

TABLE I
CFS SCALE P-VALUES FOR PERSONALITY TRAITS

Trait	CFS Scale p-value
Extroversion	0.04
Neuroticism	0.02

Fig. 3. Comparison of high and low personality trait groups based on self-reported fatigue measured by the CFS scale post-experiment

fatigue compared to introverts, highlighting the influence of personality traits on fatigue perception. Similarly, individuals with lower neuroticism consistently report reduced fatigue levels compared to those with higher neuroticism, reinforcing the critical role of personality dimensions in shaping mental fatigue outcomes.

B. Analyzing EEG power spectrum changes during experiment to assess personality-related mental fatigue

While EEG signals were acquired via a 64-electrode array, with spectral power bands quantified across all channels, this investigation specifically targets — electrodes spanning a reliable approach validated in recent studies 8 bilateral brain regions. They include the frontal (right frontal (RF), left frontal (LF)), central (right central (RC), left central (LC)), temporal (right temporal (RT), left temporal (LT)), and posterior (right posterior (RP), left posterior (LP)) regions, enabling a focused analysis of hemispheric and regional dynamics. In this study, specific brain electrodes were chosen for each region. FP2 for the right frontal (RF), F3 for the left frontal (LF), T8 and TP7 for the right and left temporal areas (RT/LT), C2 and FC5 for the right and left central regions (RC/LC), and P2 and P7 for the right and left posterior areas (RP/LP)

Table II presents a statistical analysis that compares mental fatigue between extroverts and introverts, as well as between groups with high and low levels of neuroticism. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$), indicated in bold) related to extroversion were associated with distinct power spectra in the right and left frontal lobes. Specifically, the frontal lobes showed marked differences in mental fatigue ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the beta

spectra on the TP7 electrode varied for the LT region, while the central regions exhibited differences in all power spectra, with the exception of delta in the RC lobe, and delta in the RC and beta in the LC lobe. Finally, the posterior regions demonstrated fatigue differences in all spectra except theta.

Similarly, for neuroticism, no differences in fatigue levels were found in the frontal region for either personality group. However, in the RT region, differences emerged in the beta band, while the LT region showed variations in the delta and theta bands. In the central lobe, the RC area differed in the beta band and the LC area exhibited differences across all bands. Finally, the LP region demonstrated significant differences in mental fatigue throughout the power spectrum.

Brain maps further validated mental fatigue differences. Figure 5 shows lower fatigue in extroverts, with red regions indicating increased fatigue from heightened band power. These findings align with the significant p-values in previous tables. Similarly, Fig. 4 illustrates greater fatigue in highly neurotic individuals during stress-inducing tasks.

IV. DISCUSSION

Conventional perspectives suggest that extroverts exhibit greater stress resilience and lower fatigue than introverts and emotionally unstable individuals. This study examines mental fatigue differences across personality types—extroverts versus introverts and high versus low neuroticism—using quantitative EEG analysis. EEG data were collected from 21 participants during controlled stress tasks, such as mental arithmetic and simulated job interviews. The Chalder Fatigue Scale (CFS) confirmed significant differences in subjective fatigue between the groups.

To objectively quantify fatigue, spectral power features were extracted from preprocessed EEG signals, leveraging their established role as biomarkers of cognitive exertion. Electrodes were strategically selected from bilateral brain regions to ensure regional specificity, with subsequent two-tailed t-tests applied to compare spectral power differences between cohorts. Spatial brain maps further corroborated our findings, revealing significantly lower mental fatigue in extroverted and low-neuroticism individuals relative to their introverted and high-neuroticism counterparts. This multi modal approach—integrating psychometric and neurophysiology metrics—provides novel insights into the neurocognitive correlates of personality-driven fatigue dynamics. To our knowledge, this study represents the first seminal work bridging EEG-based mental fatigue assessment with individual personality profiling, establishing a foundational framework for personalized healthcare systems tailored to neurocognitive and psychological profiles. By

TABLE II
POWER SPECTRUM ANALYSIS: HIGH VS. LOW PERSONALITY TRAIT GROUPS

Personality Traits	Spectral Bands	Frontal Region		Temporal Region		Central Region		Posterior Region	
		RF(FP2)	LF(F3)	RT(T8)	LT(TP7)	RC(C2)	LC(FC5)	RP(P2)	LP(P7)
Extroversion	delta	0.04	0.03	0.09	0.45	0.09	0.02	0.35	0.04
	theta	0.004	0.01	0.35	0.37	0.02	0.02	0.37	0.08
	alpha	0.02	0.04	0.09	0.20	0.006	0.04	0.39	0.04
	Beta	0.03	0.02	0.35	0.02	0.003	0.07	0.09	0.03
Neuroticism	delta	0.08	0.08	0.46	0.02	0.45	0.01	0.18	0.04
	theta	0.12	0.13	0.31	0.02	0.49	0.009	0.23	0.04
	alpha	0.13	0.16	0.18	0.10	0.47	0.01	0.19	0.03
	Beta	0.22	0.14	0.03	0.11	0.01	0.03	0.12	0.36

Fig. 4. Comparative Topographical Assessment of Mental Fatigue in (a) Extroverts versus (b) Introverts during Stressful Task Performance

uniquely correlating neural biomarkers with personality traits, our approach pioneers a paradigm shift in precision fatigue monitoring. Future research will expand this foundation by augmenting datasets with longitudinal analyses, integrating multi-modal physiological and psychological data from diverse cohorts, and deploying cutting-edge AI-driven analytics to refine predictive models of fatigue.

V. CONCLUSION

We introduced an innovative methodology for assessing mental fatigue across varying personality traits—specifically Extroversion and Neuroticism—by integrating the CFS scale with EEG spectral power analysis. By extracting PSD bands from meticulously preprocessed EEG signals, we established reliable biomarkers for fatigue induced by stress tasks. **Our approach not**

only distinguished extroverts from introverts and high-neurotic individuals from their low-neurotic counterparts through rigorous statistical analysis of self-reported fatigue, but it also revealed that extroverts and less neurotic participants exhibit significantly lower mental fatigue during cognitive workload. Our findings show that higher EEG band powers in introverts and high-neurotic individuals correlate with increased fatigue, offering a new perspective on linking personality traits with neurophysiological markers of mental fatigue.

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Fig. 5. Comparative Topographical Assessment of Mental Fatigue (a) More Neurotic (b) Less Neurotic during Stressful Task Performance

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